

**THE IMPORTANCE OF HUMANITARIAN IDEOLOGY IN THE
SPIRITUAL LIFE OF THE NEW UZBEKISTAN**

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Abstract: This article analyzes the role of ideology in the life and history of mankind, the ideological processes which served spiritual development and led to reforms. In addition we can study the emerging of new humanistic ideology of the new Uzbek society, the factors of its formation and the role of the social functions of ideology in uniting society on the way to great goals.

Keywords: state, society, person, ideology, humanity, social functions, process, civil society, spiritual life, New Uzbekistan.

Introduction

In the history of mankind, ideologies have performed important tasks, uniting people towards certain goals, defining goals, ideals, and normative standards of behavior. Ideology, by its nature, allows to perform many functions in the life of society. It should be noted that the ideology of state institutions and civil servants, institutions of civil society, the state and society as a whole, and a well-thought-out national ideology that unites all parts of the Uzbek society at such a responsible stage of development, should not forget that it can perform a unifying, programmatic, guiding, mobilizing, and finally protective role. In such a situation, as the head of our state, Sh. Mirziyoyev, noted that "Continuous improvement of the moral and educational level of the population, especially of our young men and women, is of the first level of importance in our society. Therefore, on the basis of the programmatic idea "From national revival to national progress", educating

young people in the spirit of loyalty to the motherland, forming initiative, dedication, and moral qualities in them is a very honorable task"[1].

S. Atamuratov's monographic investigations like "Globalization: the responsibility of protecting the nation", "Globalization and national-spiritual security"[3] study that spiritual and ideological processes in the conditions of Uzbekistan, the place of the national idea in the conditions of globalization, in addition A. Erkaev in his studies such as "Spirituality and Development", "Spirituality"[4] learns the actual tasks of spiritual development as well as O'. Abilov, A. Mukhtorov, N. Joraev, M. Kuronov, M. Yuldashova and other scientists conducted a number of scientific studies.[5] Issues of ideological expansion and the need for a national idea in the era of globalization, it has been shown that it is a vital necessity in the researches of J. Yakshikov, N. Muhammadyev [6]. Aspects of spiritual renewal related to the national ideology and social development are being researched by S. Mamashokirov, N. Khakimov, Z. Kadirova, S. Berdikulov, M. Kahhorova et al. In particular, the problems of globalization and the preservation of national identity, the relationship of spiritual development to personal maturity, the laws of spiritual development, globalization and social activity, and the dialogue of civilizations were studied in these studies [7].

The phenomenon of new Uzbekistan, the role of development strategies in the development of society, the principles of spiritual renewal and the role of ideological activity in social development are given special attention in the researches of Q. Nazarov, M. Kuronov, A. Sharipov [8].

Methods

Summarizing the level of the study of the problem of national ideologies and their formation factors, propaganda technologies and their importance in the development of society, mechanisms of combating destructive and alien ideologies in modern domestic and foreign literature, the topic of this article has been analyzed in a wide range of philosophical and political sciences. To solve them, the research used the following methods, including: problematic - chronological - the formation of ideologies, their role in the development of society, the origin of the

emergence of certain forms and methods of ideological activity. On the basis of the comparative-historical method, it is possible to emphasize the increasing complexity of ideologies, the denial of ideology in social development in some cases, its becoming a decisive force in some periods, and the increasing complexity of their classification. The method of concrete sociological research envisages the determination of the importance of national ideologies in ensuring the interests of the individual, society and the state, the trends and changes related to its development, and the logical method allows to determine the exact relations between the existing spiritual life and ideological phenomena-processes. The combined use of these methods in the subject article made it possible to investigate the existing problem more accurately and in depth.

Results and discussion

In the centuries-old history of mankind, every nation striving to build a nation-state has paid a special attention to the fact that the national idea is the basis for the implementation of the high tasks set before it, as well as for uniting and mobilizing the nation. Shavkat Mirziyoev said about this: "... the ideology of the New Uzbekistan that we are building will be primarily the ideology of humanity, goodness and creativity. Today's processes of Uzbekistan's development indicate the beginning of a new stage of the development of society and our country in the direction of national ideals and spiritual renewal."[2].

In the future, in a humanistic society, the creative essence of a person as a creator of knowledge will be manifested in a full, general and integrated form. A person's ability to fully express himself requires that the creative content of work is dominant, that is, the activity of an individual is only creative activity, creativity becomes a defining feature in the process of personal activity. In the process of creative activity prevailing in a person's life, the creative essence of a person is fully revealed. A spiritual force that can change the society of Uzbekistan, which is still viewed with distrust by some researchers, is the humanitarian ideology, or rather, the new ideological structure of the Uzbekistan state based on the humanitarian ideology. This ideology of humanitarianism expresses, first of all,

humanistic knowledge and values, which serve as a basis for changing the society of Uzbekistan. Also, on the basis of the ideology of the New Uzbekistan society, which is now being formed, the spiritual-cultural sphere, state structures, economic sphere, social and family-life sphere of the modernized Uzbekistan will be changed in the spirit of humanitarianism.

It means that in the future, in a humanistic society, all areas and structures should be changed in such a way that in all aspects of society, a person is formed and developed as a creator of knowledge, that is, it is necessary to create and build a society in accordance with the creative essence of a person, the value of everything human. For this, it is necessary to change the human activity, to change it so that only the pure creative work of a person remains. This means that in the reconstruction of the spiritual production of the future society, all non-creative types of spiritual labor will be transferred to computer systems that serve for the creative activity of a person engaged in free spiritual production. A person who is working in the field of spiritual production has only human creative activity that produces knowledge and spiritual values. In the same way, there will be a change in the quality of management activity in the government. Non-creative management work is gradually transferred to systems of automated control of social processes. With the transfer of partial management work to the systems of automated control of social processes, the creative management activity characteristic of a truly holistic person will develop. The material production of the humane society changes in such a way that the non-creative activities that do not produce knowledge are transferred to machines working in the form of closed technological processes. A person who works in the creative field of material production has only creative activity focused on the creation of new technologies.

In general, drastic and fundamental reconstruction is being carried out in all the mentioned areas of the society of Uzbekistan based on the knowledge and values of humanitarian ideology. First of all, there will be a reorientation of society's life in accordance with the highest goal of a humane society, that is, the formation of a person as a creator of knowledge, with the condition that moral and

material wealth will develop in harmony, given priority to spiritual wealth. So, it is necessary to create and build a society in accordance with the creative nature of a person. A humane person is formed as a spiritually and materially rich person, as well as a physically healthy person. In the development of personality, spiritual wealth takes priority as the basis of material wealth due to the knowledge produced by man.

The analysis of humanitarian ideology requires the analysis of the history of ideological teaching, the essence of ideology, its specific features, functions and levels of the development. In short, the essence of ideology can be interpreted as the knowledge and values underlying the development and activity of society. Ideology is not just an ideological doctrine, but the ideological structure of a whole society, its own "brain and scattered nervous system".

In researching the essence of ideology, special attention was paid to the functions and levels of development of ideologies in the world. The main functions of ideology are related to knowledge (systematization of knowledge and acquired knowledge is carried out in the forms of ideology), related to evaluation (the spiritual, moral and political values of society are evaluated in ideological teachings), related to regulation (ideology regulates the behavior of individuals and groups of people). In addition to these functions, ideologies have programmatic, unifying and driving functions. The futurological function is also of a great importance, because ideologies always give an idea of the future development of society. Ideology determines the principles of organization and management, and at the same time controls the development of society.

Knowledge and values of ideology form the basis of society's life. These ideological knowledge and values are the basis of society. Naturally, this is knowledge about the main ideology in society. Deprivation of society from ideology led to social chaos. As a result, no one knew exactly what kind of society to build and what to strive for. The prospect of social development has disappeared, and in a society without a future, leadership, powerlessness, mistrust, show of force, insolence, and violence are on the rise. In the current era of

globalization, when the struggle for the human mind and heart is intensifying, various ideological threats and attacks are appearing as a powerful tool to influence the spiritual life of our society [2].

Among the functions of ideology, it is necessary to distinguish the levels of development of ideologies. The theoretical level implies the development and inculcation of fundamental knowledge and values, which are considered the basis of this or that ideology, into the minds of individuals. The second level of ideology is related to the development and implementation of generally accepted ideological values. This level is often characterized by mass ideological propaganda. The third level of ideology requires the formation and operation of ideological values at the level of usual ideological perceptions and views. Also, in any ideological system there is a level of ideology, which is described as ideological psychology. At this level, feelings about ideology can be included.

It can be said that the analysis of the ideological structure of society has a special place in the socio-philosophical research of ideology. The structure of ideology can be defined as a clear historical integrated system of philosophical, scientific, political, aesthetic, moral, legal, economic, political, social knowledge and values about the universe, society, man, individual's place and role in the world, and the meaning of a person's life in the world. Ideology is knowledge and values that determine the decision and development of social spheres. Ideology is also a vision of the ideal construction of the future of society to which all citizens of the world should aspire. Ideological knowledge and values organize, regulate, direct and unite the activities of individuals in the spiritual, state, economic, social and family spheres of society, unite countries with different ideologies, direct interactions between the social regions of Eastern, Western and Southern civilizations. It ensures the social integrity of the globe.

Thinking about the ideology of the future society, A.A. Zinovev writes that the new society "seems itself, first of all, as a separate association with the goal of developing a new ideology (ideology of the future) and promoting it among fellow citizens, regardless of their social status, ethnicity, gender, profession and other

characteristics. should understand. Such an ideology of the future can arise in various societies, in the current conditions on the planet earth, only when the intellectual, creative and spiritual life of modern societies is at a high level. Society should have a higher goal that covers an entire era, in particular, a goal that lays the foundation for humanity's struggle for an alternative social ideal to "Westernization"[9].

Conclusion

In order to bring the society to a state of spiritual development based on the humanitarian ideology of Uzbekistan, along with all the complex difficulties and obstacles of the time, it is necessary to adopt a number of measures aimed at forming a transition society of Uzbekistan to a humanitarian society by introducing a new social order. In particular:

1. In the process of adopting a new humanistic ideology, it is necessary to adopt measures aimed at reorienting the society of New Uzbekistan from liberal-pragmatic values (acquiring common material wealth) to spiritual humanistic values, that is, it is necessary to reconstruct the society based on the ideas and principles of the humanistic ideology.
2. Promotion and inculcation of humane values aimed at suppressing anti-humane behavior, activities and "animalistic" aspirations of the citizens of the new Uzbek society.
3. Acceptance of necessary measures aimed at combating corruption in criminal-mafia structures and state apparatus based on moral and legal principles.
4. Taking measures aimed at developing the fields of education, science, art and culture in the country in order to preserve and develop the existing cultural values of Uzbekistan.
5. To change the work of the mass media in order to promote and promote a truly humane society.
6. Change ideological structures and moral propaganda departments in military and paramilitary agencies (defense, state security, internal affairs) based on humanitarian ideological values.

7. Adoption of measures aimed at strengthening state regulation of the economic sector of Uzbekistan based on market and planning mechanisms of development, as well as competition and mutual assistance.

8. For the moderate reform and development of the economic sector, it is necessary to adopt the following measures: nationalization of natural monopolies, industrial enterprises, commercial banks (by turning them into state banks or closing them).

9. Changing the economy of Uzbekistan on the basis of state, state-collective (cooperative), state-joint-stock forms of ownership, which provide the economic basis for the individual's all-round creative development, and are aimed at the development of the personal property of individuals.

10. In addition to large trade centers, nationalization of small businesses and enterprises in the field of retail trade is necessary for the continuous supply of necessary goods to the people of Uzbekistan until industrial enterprises and agriculture begin to work at full capacity.

References:

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти Шавкат Мирзиёевнинг Олий Мажлисга Мурожаатномаси Халқ сўзи, 2020 йил 24 январ.
2. Мирзиёев Ш.М. Янги Ўзбекистон стратегияси –Тошкент:, Ўзбекистон, 2021. –Б. 293, Б.273.
3. Отамуродов С. Глобаллашув: миллатни асраш масъулияти. – Тошкент: “O‘zbekiston”, 2018. – 352 б.; Глобаллашув ва миллий-маънавий-хавфсизлик” –Тошкент, Ўзбекистон, 2018.
4. Эркаев А. Маънавият ва тараққиёт. –Т.: Маънавият, 2009. –480 б.;
5. Абилов Ў. Ўзбекистон тараққиётининг оптимистик руҳи.-Т.: Истиқлол, 2003.-220-б; Мухторов А. Глобаллашув шароитида маънавий таҳдидларни бартараф этиш омиллари - Тошкент: «Маънавият», 2015. – 32 б. Жўраев Н. Тамаддунга даъват тараққиёт стратегияси. –Тошкент.: Ўзбекистон, 2018. –264 б.; Юлдашова Ф. Ўзбекистонда глобаллашув

шароитида маънавий янгиланишнинг ўзига хос хусусиятлари: фалсафа
фанлари буйича фал.докт.(PhD) дисс... автореф...–Т., 2019. –46 б.;

6. Яхшиликов Ж.Я., Муҳаммадиев Н.Э. Миллий ғоя – тараққиёт
стратегияси. Монография. – Тошкент: «Фан», 2017. – 424 б.;

7. Мамашокиров С., Тоғаев Ш. Эркин ва фаровон ҳаёт
қурилишининг ғоявий-мафкуравий масалалари. – Т.: Маънавият, 2007. – 148
б.; М. Каххорова. Ахлоқий кадриятлар ворислиги. Тошкент., 2003.-30-бет;

8. Назаров Қ.Н. Жаҳон фалсафаси қомуси. 1-китоб. – Тошкент:
“Маънавият”, 2019. – 920 б.; Назаров Қ.Н. Жаҳон фалсафаси қомуси. 2-китоб
– Тошкент: “Маънавият”, 2019. – 924 б.; М. Қуронов. Бетакроримсан,
яғонасан, она ватаним, Ўзбекистоним. –Т.: Маънавият, 2015. –160 б.;

9. Зиновьев А.А. Идеология партии будущего. С. 236-237

